

Simulated & Theoretical SNR in Passive Bistatic Noise Radar Processing

Michael J. Callahan
AFRL/RYP
2241 Avionics Circle
WPAFB, Ohio, 45433-7333 U.S.A.

Brian D. Rigling
Department of Electrical Engineering
Wright State University
3640 Colonel Glenn Highway
Dayton, Ohio, 45435-0001 U.S.A.

Muralidhar Rangaswamy
AFRL/RYP
2241 Avionics Circle
WPAFB, Ohio, 45433-7333 U.S.A.

Abstract—The theoretical output signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) values computed for cross-correlation, least-squares (LS) and various versions of the least mean square (LMS) algorithm have been found to agree with the respective output SNRs exhibited by range profile estimates generated by these algorithms in Matlab when the transmitted noise waveform's spectrum is flat. In this paper, the degree of agreement between simulated and theoretical SNRs will be shown for cross-correlation, LS, and three versions of LMS (conventional, block, and fast block) when the spectrum of the transmitted noise waveform is flat (uncorrelated, white Gaussian noise) and when it is skyline-shaped (correlated Gaussian noise).

Index Terms—cross-correlation, least squares (LS), least mean square (LMS), conventional LMS, block LMS, fast block LMS.

I. INTRODUCTION

Passive bistatic radar can be an attractive choice relative to monostatic radar due to the ability to operate covertly, immunity to jamming and interference, the ability to operate outside of traditional radar bands, and reduced cost. The benefits of noise waveforms versus classic radar waveforms such as LFM are discussed in [1]. Noise waveforms, with their thumbtack ambiguity functions, are actively being studied for use in non-cooperative passive radar. Since many digital waveforms are randomized to make their spectra approximately white, noise-like waveforms may be readily available for opportunistic use by non-cooperative passive radar receivers.

Cross-correlation may be used to compress pseudo-pulses (blocks of contiguous received signal samples), achieving range resolution. Each compressed pseudo-pulse is a superposition of shifted replicas of the cross-correlation of the direct path reference signal with the received signal (radar echoes).

The noise background includes thermal noise, noise due to hardware limitations (finite precision), and noise due to the processing technique. Using cross-correlation, the SNR for each scatterer, with the only noise present being due to the processing technique, has been shown in [2] to degrade linearly as the number of scatterers increases.

Adding a whitening filter after cross-correlation yields the least-squares (LS) algorithm. The SNR when LS processing is performed is independent of the number of scatterers. However, since LS involves a matrix inversion, it is too computationally costly to be used in practice.

As shown in [3], the LMS [4] algorithm may also be used for range profile estimation in noise radar pseudo-pulse compression. This is accomplished by treating the complex-valued range profile as an unknown channel, modeled by a finite impulse response (FIR) filter [2]. The processor within the receiver treats the illuminated scene as a linear system with unknown coefficients, which filters the transmitted signal. Given access to the transmitted waveform and the digitized backscattered signal, the receiver adaptively estimates the unknown filter coefficients, using the same processing architecture as a wireless channel identifier, and continues to update the filter coefficient values as the transmitter and receiver traverse their paths. The vector of adapted filter tap weights corresponds to the range profile of the illuminated scene [5].

The LMS algorithm converges to the LS solution in the mean [6]. It is shown in [2] that the SNR for each scatterer when LMS processing is performed is independent of the number of scatterers. This is useful when both strong and weak scatterers are present, to avoid masking of weak scatterers. Equations for SNR when cross-correlation processing and LS processing are employed are given in [3], while [7] presents equations for theoretical SNR when cross-correlation and block LMS processing are considered. The block LMS solution generalizes conventional LMS and fast block LMS. Conventional LMS is block LMS with a block size of one. Therefore, the equation for theoretical SNR when block LMS is used is valid for conventional LMS as well, for a block size equal to one. Fast block LMS is block LMS in the frequency domain, and the equation for theoretical SNR when block LMS is used is also valid when fast block LMS is used.

Much of the literature assumes that the transmitted noise waveform is white (flat spectrum) over a finite bandwidth. However, illuminators that employ analog modulation of their transmitted waveforms (such as FM broadcast transmitters) may emit waveforms that are not white. When the transmitted waveform's spectrum is colored, the cross-correlation process is likely to produce unacceptably high sidelobes. Meanwhile, LMS may produce more acceptable sidelobes.

This paper studies results obtained from cross-correlation, from conventional, block, and fast block LMS with different values of the step-size parameter μ , and from LS, when the transmitted waveform's spectrum is flat and when it has an

arbitrarily chosen (skyline) shape. This paper extends work in [8], where a notch in the spectrum caused the transmitted waveform's autocorrelation matrix to become ill-conditioned, degrading SNR. Using a skyline-shaped spectrum instead of a notched spectrum will keep the transmitted waveform's autocorrelation matrix from becoming severely ill-conditioned, since no sub-band of the skyline-shaped transmit spectrum is assigned a power spectral density of zero.

The paper is organized as follows. Section II discusses the bistatic noise radar model. Section III discusses processing architectures. Section IV presents simulation results when the transmitted noise waveform has a flat spectrum and a skyline-shaped spectrum. Section V presents conclusions.

Notation is as follows. Column vectors are denoted by underlined lower-case letters (e.g., \underline{x}). The conjugate transpose of a vector or matrix is denoted by $(\cdot)^H$ (e.g., \underline{x}^H, X^H), and complex conjugation is denoted by $(\cdot)^*$ (e.g., \underline{x}^*).

II. BISTATIC NOISE RADAR MODEL

Figure 1 provides a view of the Matlab bistatic data collection geometry used in Section IV. The simple, notional scenario consists of an airborne transmit platform, an airborne receive platform with one antenna pointed at the transmit platform to record the transmitted (reference) waveform and another antenna pointed at the scene to act as a radar receive antenna, and sixteen point scatterers on the ground (flat earth geometry), with one scatterer at scene center (0,0,0) and the others lying along the x -axis with the y and z coordinates of all sixteen scatterers equal to zero. The transmit and receive platforms, and the sixteen scatterers, all have zero velocity, because this paper focuses on the effect that a transmitted waveform's spectral shape has on zero-Doppler range profiles. For half of the cases considered, only the scatterer at scene center (0,0,0) remains in the scene (the others have been removed), while for the other half of the cases, all sixteen scatterers are in the scene. This allows us to compare algorithm performance when the transmitted waveform's spectrum is flat, and when it is not flat (skyline-shaped), when one scatterer is in the scene, and when sixteen scatterers are in the scene.

Fig. 1. Bistatic scenario geometry implemented in Matlab in Section IV. The transmit (Tx) platform (red dot), receive (Rx) platform (blue dot), and all 16 scatterers (green dots) are in the scene. This is based upon the bistatic data collection geometry shown in [2], [3], [5], and [9].

III. PROCESSING ARCHITECTURES

We can treat the problem of estimating the range profile by thinking of the illuminated scene as a system for which we want to perform channel identification to form an estimate of the filter coefficients needed to convert the transmitted (reference) waveform into the received waveform. The filter has taps, which correspond to range bins, and the filter coefficients are the tap weights which convert the tap-input vector (reference waveform) into the received (desired) signal. The vector of tap weights corresponds to the range profile.

A. Simple Cross-Correlation With Optional Whitening

If the received and reference signals, $d(n)$ and $u(n)$, are segmented into pseudo-pulses of Q samples, the estimated reflectivity at the p th range gate is computed via cross-correlation as [3]:

$$\hat{h}_q(p) = \sum_{n=q}^{q+Q-1} u^*(n-p)d(n) \quad (1)$$

where q is the first sample of a Q -sample pseudo-pulse.

The above can be written in a form used to update the tap-weight (range profile) vector on a sample-by-sample basis as:

$$\hat{\underline{h}}(n+1) = \hat{\underline{h}}(n) + \underline{u}^*(n)d(n) \quad (2)$$

where $\hat{\underline{h}}(n)$ is the previous estimate of the range profile, $\underline{u}^*(n)$ is the complex conjugate of the transmitted (reference) waveform, and $d(n)$ is the desired (received) waveform.

For a coherent integration time of T_{coh} containing Q samples, a transmit signal bandwidth of W , with M scatterers in the scene, each providing a received power at the radar receiver of σ_d^2 , and a thermal noise power of σ_z^2 at the radar receiver, the SNR of each scatterer in the scene when cross-correlation processing is used is [2], [3]:

$$SNR_{CC} = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{\sigma_d^2 W T_{coh}}{M \sigma_d^2 + \sigma_z^2} \right) \quad (3)$$

The intrinsic performance of cross-correlation can be improved by statistically “whitening” the correlator’s output. The output of the whitening operation is $\hat{\underline{h}}_{LS}(n) = (\hat{R}_u^*)^{-1} \hat{\underline{h}}_{CC}(n)$, which can be shown to be equivalent to the least-squares solution given by (14) in [7], where \hat{R}_u^* , the conjugate of the sample estimate of the autocorrelation matrix of the transmitted (reference) waveform, is equal to $E\{\underline{u}^*(n)\underline{u}^T(n)\}$.

Note the similarity to the Wiener filter, which defines the minimum mean-square error [5]:

$$\underline{w}_* = R_u^{-1} \underline{\rho}_{ud} \quad (4)$$

where \underline{w}_* is the optimum value of \underline{w} (here, \underline{w}_* represents $\hat{\underline{h}}$, the true range profile); $R_u = E\{\underline{u}(n)\underline{u}^H(n)\}$, the true autocorrelation of the tap-input vector (reference waveform) $\underline{u}(n)$; and $\underline{\rho}_{ud} = E\{\underline{u}(n)d^*(n)\}$, the true cross-correlation of the tap-input vector (reference waveform) $\underline{u}(n)$ and the conjugate of the desired (received) signal $d(n)$.

The SNR of each scatterer in the scene when cross-correlation processing is followed by whitening (making it LS processing) is [3]:

$$SNR_{LS} = 10\log_{10}\left(\frac{\sigma_d^2 WT_{coh}}{\sigma_z^2}\right) \quad (5)$$

B. Conventional LMS

Using conventional LMS, the tap-weight vector (range profile) estimate at iteration $n + 1$ is $\hat{h}(n + 1)$, computed as:

$$\begin{aligned} e(n) &= d(n) - \hat{h}^H(n)\underline{u}(n) \\ \hat{h}(n + 1) &= \hat{h}(n) + \mu\underline{u}(n)e^*(n) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where $e(n)$ is an error signal forced to zero by the LMS algorithm, $d(n)$ is the desired signal, $\underline{u}(n)$ is the tap-input vector (reference waveform), and μ is a step-size. Equation (6) converges to the Wiener solution (4) in the mean [5]. The smaller the step-size μ , the smaller the mean-square error, but the longer it will take for LMS to converge. In a dynamic environment, the true range profile will change with time, and the step-size μ must be large enough to account for changes so that the estimated range profile is kept accurate. However, too large a step-size will cause LMS to become unstable. Inequality (9.92) in [4] conservatively estimates the bounds on the step-size μ . It is repeated here, with R replaced by R_u :

$$0 < \mu < \frac{2}{\text{tr}[R_u]} \quad (7)$$

where $\text{tr}[R_u]$ denotes the trace of matrix R_u .

In the Matlab code used to generate the results, $\text{tr}[R_u]$ has been replaced by $K\sigma_u^2$, which equals $\text{tr}[R_u]$ as the number of samples used in estimating R_u goes to infinity, when the transmitted noise waveform is white Gaussian noise. This is no longer true when the samples of the transmitted waveform are correlated (such as when the transmit spectrum is skyline-shaped). In this paper, the maximum limit on step-size μ has been set to $\frac{2}{K\sigma_u^2}$, (equal to 0.02). The values of step-size μ used in this paper have been intentionally kept well below the maximum, to avoid the possibility of algorithm instability, especially when the samples of the transmitted noise waveform become correlated (non-flat spectrum) [10]. The step-sizes were set to $0.12 \cdot \mu_{\max}$ and $0.30 \cdot \mu_{\max}$, or 0.0024 and 0.006.

As stated above, conventional LMS is block LMS with a block size of one sample. From (9) and (24) in [7], replacing σ_e^2 with the receiver thermal noise power σ_z^2 , replacing σ_x^2 with the power of the transmitted noise signal σ_u^2 , with a block size of one sample, with K being the number of range bins (filter tap weights), \underline{h} being the true range profile, and h_k being the element of the true range profile at range bin k , the theoretical SNR for a scatterer at range bin k in the scene when conventional LMS processing is used is:

$$\begin{aligned} SNR_{LMS}(k) &= 10\log_{10}\left(\frac{|h_k|^2\sigma_u^2}{\sigma_z^2}\left(\frac{2}{\mu\sigma_u^2} - (K + 1)\right)\right) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

C. Block and Fast Block LMS

In [4] it was pointed out that, in block LMS, choosing the block size (the number of samples in each block) equal to the filter length (the number of range bins) is preferred in most applications. Therefore, block LMS was implemented with a block size equal to the number of range bins K in the scene. Fast block LMS, (block LMS in the frequency domain), was also implemented with a block size equal to the number of range bins K in the scene. The theoretical SNR for a scatterer at range bin k when either block or fast block LMS processing is used with a block size of K (the same result applies to both) is:

$$\begin{aligned} SNR_{\text{Block and Fast Block LMS}}(k) &= 10\log_{10}\left(\frac{|h_k|^2\sigma_u^2}{\sigma_z^2}\left(\frac{2}{\mu\sigma_u^2} - (2K)\right)\right) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

D. Learning Curves

Convergence of the LMS family of algorithms as a function of the number of iterations performed (number of samples processed) may be observed by plotting “learning curves”, which are plots of the mean-square error function J [4], which drops off exponentially, finally hovering about a steady-state value that would be reached when the number of iterations reached infinity. This will be greater than the minimum mean-square error, which could only be reached if we were able to compute the exact vector of filter tap weights (i.e. the exact range profile), instead of just an estimate.

$$J = \frac{1}{2}E\{|e(n)|^2\} \quad (10)$$

Using a smaller step-size μ will result in longer times (more input samples) being required to reach convergence, but the mean-square error will be smaller. As the transmitted waveform’s spectrum becomes less uniformly flat, the eigenvalue spread of the waveform’s autocorrelation matrix will increase, and longer times will be required for convergence.

Learning curves (not shown) for conventional, block, and fast LMS for the Section IV simulation runs indicated that, particularly for Case 4 (the skyline-shaped spectrum, 16 scatterer case), the algorithms required more input samples than were provided in order to reach convergence.

E. Independence Assumption

An independence assumption is commonly invoked when analyzing the performance of the LMS family of algorithms, whereby it is assumed that the current filter tap weight vector (estimated range profile) is independent of the current samples of the input data in the filter’s memory. This is never true in our case, due to the shift-input nature of FIR filters [10], whether or not the samples of the transmitted noise waveform are correlated with one other. For this reason, the equations for theoretical SNR that are used in this paper may yield values of expected SNR that deviate from the SNR values observed in the simulation results, particularly when the step-size μ and/or the correlation is increased.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

To illustrate the SNR achieved in simulation as well as the theoretical SNR, each averaged range profile estimate has been normalized to set its maximum peak to 0 dB, and the SNR for each profile can be visualized as the difference between its average sidelobe level and 0 dB (located at the top of its plot). Dash-dot horizontal lines marking where the theoretical average sidelobe levels would be, given the respective theoretical SNRs, are color-coded for easy matchup with the corresponding normalized averaged range profile estimates. For each of the four cases below, normalized averaged range profile estimates for the three LMS variants considered were plotted versus normalized averaged range profile estimates computed using cross-correlation and LS. Because, for each case, the block LMS and fast block LMS range profile results looked approximately the same, only the block LMS range profile results are presented, but they also represent the fast block LMS range profile results.

TABLE I
PARAMETERS USED IN THE SIMULATION

Parameter	Value
Tx/Rx/Scatterer Velocities	0.0 m/s
Avg Power of Tx Waveform	1
Each Scatterer's Avg Power at Radar Rx	0.01
Avg Rx Thermal Noise Power	0.001
Number of Range Bins	100
Center Frequency	10.0 GHz
Bandwidth of Tx Waveform	20.0 MHz
Sampling Rate	20.0 MHz
Number of Monte Carlo Realizations	1000

Table I lists some key parameters. The sampling rate was set equal to the transmitted waveform's bandwidth, because the transmitted waveform is modeled as a sequence of complex random samples, and therefore the minimum sampling rate required by Nyquist to avoid aliasing is achieved.

For the flat transmit spectrum cases below, the transmitted waveform was modeled as zero-mean, wide-sense stationary circular complex Gaussian noise in Matlab. The term "circular" means that the real and imaginary parts are jointly Gaussian, independent, and have equal variance [7]. The assumption that the transmitted waveform, and hence the signals being processed are complex is quite natural for coherent radars, because phase information must be employed in the processing [7]. Because the samples of the transmitted waveform must be independent for the waveform to have the "circular" property, having the "circular" property implies that the waveform must be spectrally white. For the skyline-shaped transmit spectrum cases below, the circular complex Gaussian noise was filtered to shape the spectrum, thus introducing correlation, and therefore the transmitted noise waveform with a skyline-shaped spectrum lost the "circular" property.

A. The Transmit Spectrum is Flat

1) *Case 1. Flat Tx Spectrum - One Scatterer:* Figure 2 shows averaged range profile estimates after normalization for the flat transmit spectrum, one scatterer case, averaged over 1000 Monte Carlo realizations, for cross-correlation, conventional LMS, and LS. The single scatterer is the one located at (0,0,0), and its radar return lies in range bin 33. Figure 3 is similar to Figure 2, but with conventional LMS replaced by block/fast block LMS.

Fig. 2. Averaged range profile estimates after normalization, by cross-correlation, conventional LMS, and LS; flat transmit spectrum; one scatterer. Solid lines are estimated range profiles; dash-dot lines are theoretical sidelobe levels.

Fig. 3. Averaged range profile estimates after normalization, by cross-correlation, block/fast block LMS, and LS; flat transmit spectrum; one scatterer. Solid lines are estimated range profiles; dash-dot lines are theoretical sidelobe levels.

2) *Case 2. Flat Tx Spectrum - Sixteen Scatterers:* Figure 4 shows averaged range profile estimates after normalization for the flat transmit spectrum, sixteen scatterers case, averaged over 1000 Monte Carlo realizations, for cross-correlation, conventional LMS, and LS. Figure 5 is similar to Figure 4, but with conventional LMS replaced by block/fast block LMS. Note in Figure 4 and Figure 5 that for cross-correlation processing, both the theoretical SNR and the SNR observed in the simulation results were reduced by about 12 dB (a factor of sixteen) compared to Case 1 by placing sixteen equal-power scatterers in the scene, instead of just one.

Fig. 4. Averaged range profile estimates after normalization, by cross-correlation, conventional LMS, and LS; flat transmit spectrum; sixteen scatterers. Solid lines are estimated range profiles; dash-dot lines are theoretical sidelobe levels.

Fig. 5. Averaged range profile estimates after normalization, by cross-correlation, block/fast block LMS, and LS; flat transmit spectrum; sixteen scatterers. Solid lines are estimated range profiles; dash-dot lines are theoretical sidelobe levels.

B. The Transmit Spectrum is Skyline-Shaped

Figure 6 shows an ideal notional skyline-shaped frequency response (blue), and the frequency response generated by the Matlab function fir2 (green), used in generating the transmitted noise waveform for Cases 3 and 4.

Fig. 6. The ideal (blue) and fir2-designed (green) skyline-shaped frequency response magnitudes in Matlab.

1) *Case 3. Skyline-Shaped Tx Spectrum - One Scatterer:* Figure 7 shows averaged range profile estimates after normalization for the skyline transmit spectrum, one scatterer case, averaged over 1000 Monte Carlo realizations, for cross-correlation, conventional LMS, and LS. Figure 8 is similar to Figure 7, but with conventional LMS replaced by block/fast block LMS. In both figures, note the range sidelobes to either side of range bin 33, which contains the radar return for the single scatterer in the scene. LS appears to be immune to the development of these unwanted range sidelobes.

Fig. 7. Averaged range profile estimates after normalization, by cross-correlation, conventional LMS, and LS; skyline-shaped transmit spectrum; one scatterer. Solid lines are estimated range profiles; dash-dot lines are theoretical sidelobe levels.

Fig. 8. Averaged range profile estimates after normalization, by cross-correlation, block/fast block LMS, and LS; skyline-shaped transmit spectrum; one scatterer. Solid lines are estimated range profiles; dash-dot lines are theoretical sidelobe levels.

2) *Case 4. Skyline-Shaped Tx Spectrum - Sixteen Scatterers:* Figure 9 shows averaged range profile estimates after normalization for the skyline transmit spectrum, sixteen scatterers case, averaged over 1000 Monte Carlo realizations, for cross-correlation, conventional LMS, and LS. Figure 10 is similar to Figure 9, but with conventional LMS replaced by block/fast block LMS. In both figures, note the range sidelobes to either side of each range bin that contains a radar return from a scatterer in the scene. These range sidelobes make it difficult to determine meaningful SNR values for the simulation results. As in Case 3, LS appears to be immune to the development

of these unwanted range sidelobes. The SNR (the difference in dB between the top of each plot at 0 dB and the average sidelobe level) achieved in simulation by each algorithm has deviated substantially from the theoretical SNR (as given by the difference in dB between the top of each plot at 0 dB and the average theoretical sidelobe level). LS performed the best, with the three LMS variants performing better than cross-correlation. One might have expected that when the LMS variants used a smaller step-size (0.0024 instead of 0.006), better performance would have been achieved here. Perhaps when the smaller step-size of 0.0024 was used for the LMS variants, not enough samples were utilized to allow the algorithms to reach convergence, which might explain the worse performance for the LMS variants in this case when the smaller step-size of 0.0024 was used.

Fig. 9. Averaged range profile estimates after normalization, by cross-correlation, conventional LMS, and LS; skyline-shaped transmit spectrum; sixteen scatterers. Solid lines are estimated range profiles; dash-dot lines are theoretical sidelobe levels.

Fig. 10. Averaged range profile estimates after normalization, by cross-correlation, block/fast block LMS, and LS; skyline-shaped transmit spectrum; sixteen scatterers. Solid lines are estimated range profiles; dash-dot lines are theoretical sidelobe levels.

V. CONCLUSION

The SNR values observed in simulation for all five algorithms agreed fairly well with the corresponding theoretical SNR values when the transmitted waveform was white Gaussian noise (flat spectrum) regardless of the number of

scatterers. When the transmitted waveform's spectrum was skyline-shaped, the range profiles exhibited sidelobe structures that sometimes made it difficult to determine meaningful SNR values, which differed from the corresponding theoretical SNR values by a greater degree than when the transmit spectrum was flat.

Algorithm performance depended upon the condition number of the transmitted waveform's autocorrelation matrix, with performance generally becoming worse as the transmit spectrum became less flat. A white Gaussian noise waveform (flat spectrum) has a diagonal autocorrelation matrix, with all of the elements on the main diagonal being equal, resulting in a well-conditioned matrix, while a transmit waveform having a non-flat spectrum may have (due to correlation) an ill-conditioned autocorrelation matrix due to a large disparity between the maximum and minimum eigenvalues of the matrix, causing poor SNR performance.

As expected, the simulated and theoretical SNR for each scatterer when using cross-correlation processing decreased by about 12 dB as the number of equal-power scatterers increased from one to sixteen, while the LS and LMS results were not influenced by the change in the number of scatterers.

REFERENCES

- [1] T. Thayaparan, M. Dakovic, and L. Stankovic, "Mutual interference and low probability of interception capabilities of noise radar," *IET Radar, Sonar and Navigation Special Issue on Signal Processing in Noise Radar Technology*, vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 294–305, 2008.
- [2] B. Rigling, "Intrinsic processing gains in noise radar," *IEEE Waveform Diversity Conference*, Lihue, HI, January 2006.
- [3] B. Rigling, "Performance prediction in adaptive noise radar," pp. 3–7, 38th Asilomar Conference on Signals, Systems, and Computers, November 2004.
- [4] S. Haykin, *Adaptive Filter Theory*. Prentice Hall Information and System Sciences Series, 3rd ed., 1996.
- [5] B. Rigling, "Adaptive filtering for air-to-ground surveillance," in *Algorithms for Synthetic Aperture Radar Imagery XI* (E. Zelnio and F. Garber, eds.), pp. 53–61, Proceedings of SPIE Vol. 5427, SPIE, Bellingham, WA, 2004.
- [6] A. H. Sayed, *Fundamentals of Adaptive Filtering*. John Wiley and Sons, Inc., 2003.
- [7] M. Meller and S. Tujaka, "Processing of noise radar waveforms using block least mean squares algorithm," *IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems*, vol. 48, pp. 749–761, January 2012.
- [8] M. Callahan, B. Rigling, and M. Rangaswamy, "Impact of processing approach on SNR performance for passive bistatic noise radar," pp. 0805–0810, *IEEE International Radar Conference*, 2015.
- [9] B. Rigling, "Adaptive noise radar for simultaneous bistatic SAR and GMTI," in *Algorithms for Synthetic Aperture Radar Imagery XII* (E. Zelnio and F. Garber, eds.), vol. Proceedings of SPIE Vol. 5808, pp. 166–177, SPIE, Bellingham, WA, 2005.
- [10] S. C. Douglas and W. Pan, "Exact expectation analysis of the LMS adaptive filter," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 43, pp. 2863–2871, December 1995.